

Giant weed (*Calotropis* sps.) an economical and eco-friendly method of pest management in organic farms.

Jawale C.S., Dama L. B., Joshi Chaitanya N.,

Address

1 C. S. Jawale
Zoology Department
HPT Arts & RYK Science College, Nashik-422005

2 L. B. Dama
Zoology Department
D. B. F. Dayanand College of Arts and Science, Solapur 413002

Address for correspondence

Dr. Chetan S. Jawale
P.G. Department of Zoology
HPT Arts & RYK Science College,
Nashik 422005 (M. S)
INDIA
Email: csjawale@hotmail.com
Tel. Phone: 91-253-2571989, 9422770869

Abstract: *Calotropis* species (Family *Asclepiadaceae*) commonly known as Giant weed is widely distributed throughout the India. In every State farmers are using this bio-resource for the control of variety of pest including insects, nematodes, bacterial and fungal plant diseases. It has also been used in veterinary practices at farm level. Concise data of all such varied use of *Calotropis* sps, their formulation and application doses are discussed.

Keywords: *Calotropis*, bio-farms, Pest control, extracts.

Introduction

Calotropis species (family *Asclepiadaceae*) commonly known as giant weed is widely distributed throughout the India. In every state farmer are using this bio-resource for the control of variety of pest including insects, nematodes, bacterial and fungal plant diseases. It has also been used in veterinary practices at farm level. Concise data of all such varied use of *Calotropis* sps, their formulation and application doses are discussed.

Calotropis is known as gigantic swallow wort, rubber bush, apple of Sodom, King crown, Roost tree in English; Ark, Mandar, Alark, Mada, Shookphal, etc in Sanskrit, Akoa, Aakvan and Akha etc in hindi; Rui and Aakda in marathi, Aakdo in Gujarathi and akando in Bengali. It is a shrub, about four meters in height; exude copious milky sap when cut or broken. leaves opposite; flowers waxy violet or white; petals five, purple tipped inside and with a central purplish crown; fruits gray green, 8-10 cm long, containing numerous seeds with tufts of long silky hairs at one end (Perry 1980). It contains calotropin, an active poison of the digitalis type. Latex contains traces of glutalione and a

prodeoclastic enzyme. Root bark contains 13-amyirin, 2-isomeric crystalline alcohol, gigantol and isogiganteol. Flowers contain esters of alpha and 13-calotropeols and 13-amyirin (Anon. 1986).

For termite control (Vajrakannu 2001)

Calotropis procera leaf extract at 20% solution for the dipping of sugarcane was found effective. Sprinkling of 2% solution of plant extract in soil, just before the sugarcane plantation was found effective. Plant material soaked in water for at least 24 hrs, filtered and poured on termites infected soil was found effective.

As an insecticides (Srivastava et. al, 2006)

1) 5 kg of *Calotropis procera*, 5 kg Keemp (*leptadenia pyrotechnica*) twigs, 1 kg of salt and 10 liters cow urine are crushed together and packed in airtight earthen pot, placed in manure pit for 15 to 20 days. The suspension is filtered through cotton cloth and filtrate is applied as an insecticide along with irrigation water at 10 liter solution for 1 ha to control soil dwelling insects.

2) The latex of *Calotropis gigantea* diluted with 15 parts of water and sprayed on cotton crops effectively controls caterpillars within three days.

3) A Moth old decayed extract of leaf is used to treat sap sucking insects in sugarcane with no side effects. This treatment cures the disease with in 2-3 days.

4) Application of leaf powered at 50 kg/ ha in mustard was found effective to control mustered saw fly (*Athalia proxima*)

As attractant for pest (Jani 1992)

When leaves of *Calotropis procera* are placed in paddy field they attract aphids. Long branches with leaves are placed at a distance of 14.6 meter in paddy fields; the branches are changed thrice. *Calotropis* leaves are spread in filed infested with army worm (Katara). Next day insects gather on the leaves are collected and replaced. Twigs of *Calotropis giagantea* are used as tap in caster, sesamum and ground nut in rainy season to attract red hairy caterpillar due to smell of leaf latex. The larvae are collected and burnt.

As repellent for borers (Srivastava et, al. 2006)

Calotropis procera branches are placed at the water inlet of paddy field to control stem and root borer insect pest. *Calotropis* is planted in ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) filed to repel attack of insect pests.

For blight disease of plants (Rathod 2001)

Equal quantities of leaves of *Calotropis procera*, Neem and aloe-vera (*Korphad*) are ground to make a homogenous mixture. Such 500 ml of the plant mixture is diluted in 15 liter of water with 5 gm of washing powder. It is sprayed at 8 -10 days regular interval to prevent blight disease (Karpa) on crops.

For bud necrosis disease (Srivastava & Singh 1995)

Spraying of aqueous leaf extract at 1% with in 40 days of germination (two sprays) reduced the bud necrosis disease in groundnut.

For plant nematode control (Srivastava et, al. 2006)

Soil application of leaf powder at 100 kg/ha reduced the root knot nematode up to considerable extent in pigeon pea.

For Grass lawns in gardens and nurseries (our experiment)

5 kg of *Calotropis* leave, 2 kg of *Parthenium* flowers, smeared in the 20 liters of water and added 5 liters of cow urine; the mixture is mixed and allows standing in plastic drum for around 20 days. The decayed molasses were filtered through the cores cotton cloth, and stored in plastic bottles. It is diluted 10 times to treat lawn for the ground insect and flies control. The pretreatment with above extract was done before planting lawn in the area, after 1 month , 15 times diluted filtrate is used for spraying purpose, and later the boundaries were drenched with 10 times diluted filtrate to prevent entry of termites and ants in the lawn area. Through this treatment, it was found that there is complete eradication of termites, ants and white flies from the lawn. The name “**Mahbali Arka**” is given to this extract because the *Calotropis* leaves were collected from the waste of Lord Hanuman temples in the Nasik City.

Conclusion: *Calotropis* is proved prospective bio-pesticide plant. Traditionally it has been used by farmers without knowing its chemical properties, when formulated with some more poisonous plants in the local area it proved effective bio-pesticide for most of the agricultural and nursery pest. More investigation on the different formulations has to be done. This is an attempt to transfer scientific and traditional knowledge to our farmers.

Reference:

1. Srivastava S. K., Attri B. L. Pandey Hema. (2006). Indigenous wisdom for the use of Giant weed in disease and pest management. Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge Vol. 5(1), January 2006, pp. 83-86
2. Vajrakannu V K, (2001). Termite Control by *Calotropis*. Honey Bee , 12 (1) (2001), 27.
3. Jani B, (1992). *Calotropis gigantia* and caterpillar in cotton, Honey Bee , 3 (3) (1992), 17.
4. Rathod P G, (2001). Control of blight in *cumin* crop, Honey Bee, 12 (2) (2001), 10.
5. Srivastava S K & Singh A B, (1995). Status and control strategy to peanut bud necrosis disease in Uttar Pradesh, in: Recent Studies on peanut bud necrosis disease, Ed Buiel A A M, Parlevliet J E and Lenne J M, (ICRISAT Asia Centre, Pattancheru, Andhra Pradesh), 1995, 65.
6. Srivastava S K, (2004). Utilization of plants and their bi-products as traditional knowledge for eco-friendly environment, Sabujima, 12 (2004), 82.
7. Perry LM. (1980). Medicinal plants of East and South East Asia: attributed properties and uses. MIT (1980) Press. South East Asia.
8. Anon. (1986). The useful plants of India. Publications & Information Directorate (1986), CSIR, New Delhi, India.